

A Role of Education in Rural Development

P. Rajeswari

MBA, Ph.D. (Finance)
Rishi UBR Women's College, Kukatpally

Abstract

Education is the mirror of the society and is the seed as well as flower of the socioeconomic development. It transforms human beings from ignorance to illumination, from revenant of social backwardness to light of social enhancement and a nation from underdevelopment to faster social and economic development. A rural development goal is to improve the well being or standard of living of rural people by increasing income earning opportunities in rural areas. The role of education in rural development is prominent by its impact on employment and income. Illiteracy is a grave obstacle to social and economic development. Education is the true sorcery that can bring India its next golden age. The motto is explicit. All for knowledge, and knowledge for all. With education, the rural population can apply new knowledge and implement better technology and practices into their businesses. This will even help in bringing the per capita income of the country up and reducing poverty.

Education has a desirable controlling influence over development of the rural individual, family, community, and society, leading to reduced poverty, income equity, and controlled, unemployment. The failure of dribbling, development and recognition of the importance of rural areas and rural people to the economic unfettering of developing countries has given education a key role in rural systems of supply, production, marketing, personnel maintenance, education, health care, and governance. Functions of education include imparting social change, improving individual social position and standard of living, activating participation in rural and cultural development.

Keywords: Development, UNSCEO, Literacy, Education Transforms, Amelioration

Introduction

Education is the guiding light as well as the best investment one can make. But not everyone is fortunate to do so. Education is a basic right but the reality is that only a small fraction of the population is able to access it. A majority of them in India live in the rural backdrop with minimal facilities and education is one of them. However, the time is changing and the government is trying to bring them out of peril by fostering rural education through a variety of schemes.

Objectives of the Study

Educational objective of this study is to increase the level of rural development from educational institutions to economic agents involved in projects and activities that preserve the environment towards achieving the sustainable development goals an education system in rural communities has the opportunity to build capacity and knowledge in the rural populace helping them to make informed decisions about their farms and to innovate in agricultural affairs education also exposes the masses to information and helps prevent the misinterpretation of information.

Definition of Education

Education means education is the expression of complete development of man through education current of willpower can be controlled positively education should be looked upon as a development of different powers not in the memory of words collection education teaches a man to contemplate in the right direction education is not the name of accumulation of facts and data but its essence should appear in the mental concentration education makes the men purifies and develops the character makes a man cultured and civilized.

Education Provides Trained Manpower from Rural Areas

Rural development requires educated manpower with a rural background but undoubtedly almost all the rural areas or regions in developing countries are desperately short of highly trained manpower with rural background it is also important to have enough manpower for specific occupations in rural development activities obviously rural development is calling for advanced educational preparation at the rural cultural understanding level the obvious reasons for limited supply of trained manpower is the shortage of quality schools in rural areas if more schools are built it is assured that they will contribute to greater cultural understanding and a larger supply of trained manpower for rural development from rural.

Research Methodology

Sources of Data

Secondary Data: Collect the data from different sources like text books, magazines, research papers, websites.

The articles reviewed different articles like industry practitioner papers and policy reports. The selection of articles was done manually. A systematic search was conducted on Google Scholar using article abstract search and a search on the body-of-articles.

Need of Education for Rural Development in India

Education in the rural segments is not only important to eradicate poverty and illiteracy but also for a variety of other social economic as well as cultural and political reasons education plays an important role in enlarge refine the availability of jobs in rural areas enhance rural productivity and wages raising the living standards of the under privileged the basic needs elementary education, healthcare, clean drinking water, rural roads etc. Education opens up new opportunities to access new information and technology that enables an individual to make the right decisions in both personal and professional life it allows children to understand policies rights laws from the young age which will be helpful in the future as 65 of the population of India is situated in rural areas emphasizing on rural education will help boost the overall economy furthermore it will also help in reduce migration of people from rural areas to cites of employment and create new opportunities in fact many of the developed countries have very active rural development programs it diagnosis their needs assert their rights and take greater control of decisions effecting their lives providing manpower in rural areas linking rural and urban areas providing employment and income opportunities increasing labor force productivity and develop leadership.

How Education Impacts Rural Development

If people in rural areas get high-quality education then they will be able to become more eligible for both public and private sectors. Most of the rural households are engulfed with the problem of poverty and it becomes extremely essential for them to get a job. Learning is the major factor which is related to education. If one learns new things then he can educate more people. Without education, one can not explore new

ideas. It means, he is not able to develop the world; without ideas, there is no creativity and without creativity there is no development.

How can Rural Education be Improved

Education is a dynamic process that starts from birth a child is surrounded by parents and other siblings and experiences his surroundings and responds the surrounding environment the physical and social environment imparts information and the child tries to learn from that information and responds from those responses we assess whether his/her development is normal abnormal or extraordinary different children at the same biological age respond differently to the same environment education is a dynamic process that starts from birth a child is surrounded by parents and other siblings and experiences his surroundings and responds the surrounding environment the physical and social environment imparts information and the child tries to learn from that information and responds from those responses we assess whether his/her development is normal abnormal or extraordinary different children at the same biological age respond differently to the same environment. Here are 5 ways to upgrade the rural education system:

1. Boost free education
2. Establish more schools
3. Work on school infrastructure
4. Bring innovative teaching methods
5. Promote computer literacy

National Policy on Education 1986

Founder of NPE-1986 Rajeev Gandhi introduced one of the most important education policies in India - the National Education Policy 1986. Similar to the 1968, this one too aimed to promote education amongst Indians.

The NEP-1986 recommends that the institutions of national importance like UGC, NCERT, NIEPA, AICTE, ICAR, IMC etc. are strengthened to enable them to give shape to national system of education and to cope with the emerging demands of the nation. The parliament, during the budget session in 1986, discussed and adopted the national policy on education in 1986. A promise was made at that time by the minister of human resource development that he would present in the monsoon session a programme of action. For the implementation of the policy immediately after the budget session, the ministry undertook an intensive exercise to prepare the promised programme of action.

The Right to Education

The right to children for free and compulsory education (RTE Act 2009), which represents the consequential legislation, envisaged under article 21-A, means every child has a right to full time elementary education of satisfactory and equitable quality in a formal school which satisfies certain essential norms. Main features of Right to Education 2009 were free and compulsory education to all children of India in the 6 to 14 age group, no child shall be held back expelled or required to pass a board examination until the completion of elementary education. The law came into effect in the whole of India except the state of Jammu and Kashmir. From 1st April 2010, first time in the history of India, a law was brought into force by a speech by the then prime minister Manmohan Singh. Uttar Pradesh will become the first state in the country to implement the Right to Education Act 2009 that calls for free and compulsory primary education to children in the age group of 6 to 14.

Sarva Siksha Abhiyan (SSA)

A few important facts about SSA are mentioned in the list below:

1. SSA is termed as an education for all movement.
2. The pioneer of the SSA programme was Atal Bihari Vajpayee, the former Indian prime minister.
3. The central government, in partnership with state governments, is implementing this initiative.
4. The initial aim of SSA was to meet its objectives by 2010, however the timeline has been extended.
5. SSA aims to provide educational infrastructure to around 193 million children in 11 million habitations.
6. 86th amendment act to the Indian constitution provided legal backing to SSA when it made education free and compulsory for children in the age group of 6 to 14.
7. New Education Policy 2020 aims to bring about two cores out of school children into the mainstreams.
8. In the National Education Policy of 2019, it was mentioned that an estimated 62 crore children of school age between 6 and 18 years were out of school in 2015.
9. “Padhe Bharat, Badhe Bharat” is a sub-programme of SSA.
10. There is a government portal under the name Shagun that has been launched to monitor the SSA programme. The world bank in association with the ministry of HRD developed it.

Education System in Rural India

As of 2021, the literacy rate in rural India was around 73.5%, this includes 81% male and 65% female literacy in rural section of India. As the rural economy currently contributes to 25% to 30% of the country's GDP, literacy in these parts is important for the Indian economy.

The Challenges of Education in Rural India and How Technology can Help Overcome them

For the large majority of the population living in rural areas, education is highly dependent on government-run or aided schools and non-governmental organizations. But rural areas still face various barriers that directly impact the countries literacy rate. The National Education Policy 2020 emphasizes digital learning as an alternative to the conventional classroom model. But implementing this in rural India will face some challenges.

Primary Education System in India

Primary education in India is divided into two parts, namely - lower primary (class 1-4) and upper primary / middle school (class 5-8). The Indian government lays emphasis on primary education class 1 to 8, also referred to as elementary education, to the 6 to 14 years old children.

National Educational Policy 2020

The ministry of human resource development formed a committee chaired by Dr. K. Kasturirangan for preparing the National Education Policy (NEP). The committee was constituted in June 2017. The committee submitted its report on May 31, 2019. The union cabinet approved the NEP in July.2020. This policy will usher in sweeping changes to the education policy of the country, including a renaming of the Ministry of Human Resource Development as the Education Ministry. The union cabinet has approved the new National Education Policy 2020 with an aim to introduce several changes in the Indian education system from the school to the college level. It aims at making India a global knowledge superpower. The new education policy cleared by the cabinet is only the third major revamp of the framework of education in India since independence. The two earlier education policies were brought in 1968 and 1986.

National Educational Policy 2022

The NEP 2022 is based on four pillars, which are access, equity, quality and accountability. In this new policy, there will be a 5+3+3+4 structure which comprises 12 years of school and 3 years of Aanganwadi (pre-school), replacing old 10+2.

1. Foundational stage: 5 years
2. Preparatory stage: 3 years
3. Middle stage: 3 years
4. Secondary stage: 4 years

Conclusion

Education is a very important factor to bring this change in rural environment. This paper describes the most important role of education in rural development. In fact rural development as a process depends on a large number of variables of which education is one. Education should be placed first and foremost in the services of democracy which demands not only that the citizen be protected against arbitrary decisions but also that he/she take part in decisions which affect the future of his/her society.

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